

Uncovering Consumers in Organized Retail Sector in India

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to promote understanding of types of consumers in India in organized retail sector. The main objective of the study was to identify and categorize the types of consumers visiting the organized retail stores. For collecting the primary data, at each store 30 samples were selected for this purpose based on convenience. The data collection method was an informal interview and discussions with consumers for about 15 to 20 minutes at the exit door of the three identified organized retail stores operating in Ahmadabad. The original identity of the respondents and store is disguised by coding. The findings of the consumers' categories were identified through the conversational interviews. The consumers were then finally categorized based on findings are described as, Economic Consumers, Hedonist Consumers, Moralistic Consumers, Active (Involved) and Inactive Consumers, Definite and Indefinite Consumers, Individualistic Consumers, Recreational Consumers. There was an implicit recognition of qualitative data management as an iterative process.

Keywords: Organized Retailing, Consumer Types, India

1. Introduction

Today in the highly competitive market, the growth and survival of any organization in any industry exceedingly depends on how well it understands its customers and responds to their current and potential needs. In the retail industry, understanding the retail customers plays an important role in the success of a retail store. In the Q&A at India Retail Forum 2008 Kishore Biyani enumerated gist and number of issues concerning retail business in India. He had highly stressed that retailing is all about understanding the consumers and success depends on it. The development of technology and globalization has led to a new era of consumerism where retailers focus completely on meeting the needs, wants and priorities of the consumer. It is important to know about the market and the various factors influencing the buying behavior of a retail customer Anonymous (2008).

As such all the consumers are potential consumers for the retail business, but more important is to identify the group of consumers who will become actual customers or purchasers within their outlets. Such different groups have distinct needs and wants may be because of their consumption pattern, demographics (like age profile, working patterns, income and expenditure, occupation), lifestyle changes, buying process, shopping behavior, shopping motivations and objectives, changing consumer among other.

It is claimed by Abercrombie et al. al., (1994) that modern societies are increasingly organized around consumption and therefore the trends in consumption pattern have emerged over a period of time which are very significant for retailers to observe and understand. The trends in consumption pattern describe how the consumers change over time and make predictions about how consumers will consume in the future. So, retailers need to comprehend the consumer profile. India's National Council for Applied Economic Research estimated that the nation's middle class population currently comprises about 17 million households – 90 million people – with annual earnings ranging between \$4,500 and \$22,000. An additional 287 million could be termed as 'aspirers' or those that hope to join the middle class in the near term. Thus rising incomes, particularly in the lower and middle-income households, are impacting retail consumers in India as these groups tend to spend more on upgrading and diversifying their lifestyles, eating out and moving on to processed and convenience items.

Generally it is perceived that consumers go for simple necessity to purchase the physical goods. But Tauber (1972) found through his research 'why do people shop?' realizing that were other reasons than the need to buy the simple physical goods. He found consumers' motivations for shopping are resulting from many factors, some of them are less associated

to the buying of products, and more connected to personal and social motivations of individuals.

The purpose of the present study is to present an interrogative analysis of consumers' categories in Ahmadabad city of Gujarat. It also focuses on the describing consumers psychological and demographical characteristics. The focus of the research was qualitative in nature. A quantitative approach seeks a broad set of general findings and may give notice to the experiences of the individual as insignificant (Burns & Grove, 1993). However, there are various studies conducted in the similar line (for example, Stone (1954), The Chicago Tribune (1955), Stephen and Willet (1969), Darden and Reynolds (1971), Darden and Ashton (1975), Moschis (1976), Williams, Painter, and Nicholas (1978), Bellenger and Koargaonkar (1980), Westbrook and Black (1985), Lesser and Hughes (1986), AGB (1987), Cullen (1990), Kirk-Smith & Mak (1992), Jerratt (1996)). The main objective of the study was to identify and categorize the types of consumers visiting the organized retail stores. Thus, research focuses on how understanding of such categorized consumes is useful to the organized retailers.

2. Literature Review

It is very evident that market consists of a large variety of consumers. These consumers are different in various aspects, like, education, age, profession, locality, culture, and so on. For instance, Arnold (1997) found significant differences between the demographic profiles (e.g. age, education, household size) of large-format department store shoppers as compared to non-shoppers. A few more studies have examined the effect of consumer demographics on retail format choice in the grocery context. Zeithaml (1985) conducted a field study to examine the effects of five demographic variables (gender, female working status, age, income, marital status) on supermarket shopping variables (e.g. shopping time, number of supermarkets visited weekly, amount of money spent). It has been found that consumers differ in their shopping behavior. The consumers can be classified into different categories, like, Sinha and Uniyal (2007) have discussed in their research study. They have identified them as under:

- a) Choice Optimizer: This type of consumers tries to obtain the greatest from their shopping activities.
- b) Premeditated Shoppers: The consumers constituting this group go straight to specific racks or a particular section in a store.
- c) Economizing Shoppers: Highly price conscious shoppers are economizing shoppers. Mainly they are found constrained by their budget,

- d) Support Seekers: These types of consumers belong to the shoppers who likely to demonstrate low confidence while making purchase decisions.
- e) Frequent Shoppers and Infrequent Shoppers: There are various studies that have classified the shoppers according to frequency of their visits to the retail stores for purchasing. Frequent shoppers enter the store very confidently and move around comfortably. Mostly the infrequent shoppers look around the store, ask for directions, and rush towards the shopping area or section as soon as the sales person provides the direction.
- f) Recreational Shoppers: To stay at the store and enjoying the store atmosphere is one objective of these shoppers. While shopping processes, they try to obtain maximum recreational value.

Sinha and Uniyal (2007) have shown in their book on retailing that mostly, shopping orientation has been used widely to profile the consumers. The way consumers do shopping is indicated by their shopping orientations. Solomon (1994) has identified several general shopper types. Although his work focused on western populations, it gives the general idea about them. They are:

- a) The economic shopper: A rational, goal-oriented shopper who is primarily interested in maximizing the value of his or her money.
- b) The personalized shopper: A shopper who tends to form strong attachments to store personnel.
- c) The ethical shopper: A shopper who likes to help out the underdog and will support locally owned stores against big chains.
- d) The apathetic shopper: One who does not like to shop and sees it as a necessary but unpleasant chore.
- e) The recreational shopper: A person who views shopping as a fun, social activity—a preferred way to spend leisure time.

3. Research Methodology

To apprehend the determined objectives, an in-depth literature review was carried out using the available secondary data including the internet resources. For collecting the primary data from consumers, at each store 25 consumers were selected for this purpose based on their convenience. Consumers were asked various questions relating to their

buying habits, spending orientations, brand preferences, likings, purpose of visit, and their overall behavior. The data collection method was informal interviews and discussions with consumers for about 15 to 20 minutes at the exit door of three identified organized retail stores.

The informal interview was chosen as a means of collecting data from the respondents. In this way, better idea on the part of the topic, the researcher could identify directly (Brenner et al. 1985). To get and ensure the right direction of the conversation, the researchers had used a check list containing 7-8 questions. The original identity of the respondents is disguised and consumers' transcripts are coded as A1, A2, A3, A4, B1, B2, B3, B4, C1, C2, C3, C4, and so on, using alphanumeric. Each interview was transcribed verbatim. Before taking an interview, the researchers have taken the oral consent of the respondent.

Population and Sample

The sample was drawn from consumers visiting at the organized retail stores. From this population, convenience samples of 30 respondents were selected. The sample consisted of both the gender and the sample size is considered acceptable for an exploratory study (Mason 1996). The respondents were chosen to represent the typical experience of the population from which they were drawn. Convenience sampling method was used to identify the respondents and to get information required. The decision to use this method may be criticized, for example Morse (1991) suggests that such a selection process is biased. It can, however, be argued that such bias was used positively to ensure that data are as accurate and complete as possible.

Data Analysis

It is recognized that data analysis in qualitative methodology begins with a need for familiarity with the data. To increase reliability of findings, the following procedure was used. To begin with, the transcripts were managed phrases and words were grouped together in common themes. The broad themes to emerge from the analysis were different types of consumers like:

- Economic Consumers
- Hedonist Consumers
- Moralistic Consumers
- Active and Inactive Consumers
- Definite and Indefinite Consumers
- Individualistic Consumers
- Recreational Consumers

There was an implicit recognition of qualitative data management as an iterative process.

Limitations of the Study

The study was undertaken at the exit door of the selected retail store, predominantly male respondents were 60 percent of the total respondents, and thus there is a gender bias to our study which may benefit from the further exploration or the research. Though due care was taken by the researchers at the time of data collection and documentation, it is possible to have an error of misinterpretation or missing at all some part of data and therefore biasness in the study. The sample size of 75 although acceptable for exploratory study, does limit the study's claims of general descriptive representativeness. Nevertheless, strong broad themes emerged from the collected and explored supported the some of the past studies and warrant further exploration.

4. Findings and Results

The findings of the consumers' categories were identified through the conversational interviews. There were many differences across the samples. In general, the findings suggest that the consumers may be because of their socio-economic, psychological, and demographical background and sometimes it was previous experiences. The consumers were then finally categorized based on findings are described as under:

Economic Consumer

According to the findings of research, in retailing an economic consumer can be defined as the consumers who decide to buy or shop in a cost-effective way and make balanced choices, in a more simple language spending their money wisely. The economic consumers are apparent from the following metaphors:

- I buy only those products which I get at lower prices. - A3
- The schemes offers on Wednesday attract me to visit this store especially on it. - B8
- I normally wish to spend my money after necessary products only. I spend carefully. - C5

Utility is a term used to measure the amount of return a consumer gains from a good or service they choose to spend for, thus spending their money wisely, in retailing terms is a method of maximizing consumers own utility. They can also be termed as rational consumers.

Hedonistic Consumer

The research suggests that such kinds of consumers are thinking that they are persons who: like to have some extra

because I deserve it, buy on impulse, and like shopping for new things.

These types of consumers have elements of shopping and impulse buying, and self-gifts because the person means that she or he deserves it. The hedonistic consumer is described as pleasure loving or self-indulgent and a person with high consumption measured in costs. This is supported by Brusdal and Randi (2005) and Kaul (2006) in their research work. While conversation some of the consumers expressed,

- I purchased two Punjabi Suits last week when I came with my friend to accompany her for shopping. Really I liked them very much at first sight only. - A1
- Whenever I visit this store, I always look for the new products like instant food products, wrist watches, styles of clothes, and so on. - C9

Moralistic Consumer

Moralistic consumers purchase intentionally the products and services that the customer considers to be made ethically. This may mean with minimal harm to or exploitation of humans, animals and/or the natural environment. They are also sometimes regarded as "Ethical Consumers", their buying behavior is bifurcated as 'positive buying' in which ethical products are favored, or 'moral boycott', that is negative purchasing and company-based purchasing. The moralistic consumers are evident from the following phrases.

- I prefer to purchase the handicraft items (files, folders, pens, table pieces etc...) made by women or children. - A8
- Plastic packs must be banned as they are spoiling the environment. - C6

The moralistic consumers were found more principle based while shopping the products. It was observed that the term moralistic consumer may be considered as an emerging and wider movement within retailing, which means that large corporations wish to be seen as working ethically, should try for improving the ethical standards of their business.

Active and Inactive Consumer

The research proposed that there are also consumers who are active and assertive, not passive. They are very careful about their purchases. Before making any purchase decision, they check all the major criteria like, price, discount offers, quality, quantity, product features, brand, etc. Such consumers commented;

- I knew about the offers on electronics, I had read about it in the yesterday's Gujarat Samachar. This is the best offer I have seen ever. - A4
- While shopping I always look at the brand of the product and the manufacturing company. - B3
- I come for shopping rarely; it is a job of my wife. I am not much attentive while purchasing household items. - C7

They also perform comparative analysis based on above mentioned parameters. The involved consumers are also aware that how marketers trying to attract them. The adverse was also found from the consumers, which were labeled as inactive consumers. Solomon (1994) has identified several general shopper types in his work where he named inactive consumers as apathetic shoppers.

Definite and Indefinite Consumers

The research findings contained repeated indications based on the narrow (specific) and broad (unspecific) choices of products. The consumers constituting a group go straight to specific racks or a particular section in a store, defined as definite consumers. They seem to be as they have narrow choice of product set. Such type consumers ask for the specific product or service and generally do not compare with any of the options. They are well determined in advance about their shopping. These types of consumers are noticeable from their statements;

- I do not waste time in shopping; I just go to the sections from where I will buy. - A7
- I always buy Surf Excel washing powder. - B10
- While buying my apparels, I mostly come with my friends as they help me in identifying best and suitable color combinations. - C1

The research unfolded another category of consumers termed as indefinite consumers, such consumers are those who normally show low confidence while making purchase decisions. They either need help from the accompanying person or takes an opinion of store personnel to take a purchase decision. Normally, before making any kind of decision they consult a lot with others.

Individualistic Consumers

The individualistic consumers defined as positively interpersonal, a closeness of relationships between the customer and personnel. Such types of consumers contact to the salesperson that is paying personal attention while he is purchasing. They seek individualized and extra care from the store personnel. They also believe in the long term relationship with the store personnel. Solomon (1994) stated

such consumers as personalized shoppers, describing as more attachment to store personnel. Individualistic consumers stated as under:

- The salespeople are very cooperative; I am satisfied because they pay personal attention. - A6
- The smiling face of salespeople makes shopping delightful. - C3

Recreational Consumers

The research findings suggested that consumers visit to enjoy the store atmosphere. It simply gives them pleasure and joy. Such consumers try to get maximum recreational value while purchasing at the stores. Looking at the merchandise display, layout arrangement, store ambience and atmosphere they obtain pleasure. Their visits to the store last longer spending maximum time, they also see, read, listen, and take trials of almost everything that is possible and on display. These findings are similar with the studies carried by Sinha and Uniyal (2007) Solomon (1994). The recreational consumers are visible from the following metaphors:

- The environment inside the store is very cool and pleasant. - A2
- I normally spend three to four hours while I come for shopping in this store because I like to visit all the sections and sometimes I just pass time inside. - B5

5. Conclusion

Retailing activity is known in general, as a process of selling goods and services to the final consumers for their personal, or their family's consumption. Therefore, it is in the interest of every retailer to gather as much as possible information allowing the understanding of the final consumers so that the goods and services offered remains relevant to the consumers. To conclude, Gilbert (2002) has rightly motioned in his book, it is important to realize that no retail organization can be effective unless it has a complete understanding of the way retail consumers make decisions and act in relation with the consumption of the retail products. The term 'consumer' seems to be singular but in reality there is wide variety of consumers. The retailers need to study consumer types to be aware of: the needs as well as the purchase motives of the individuals, how demographic change may affect retail purchasing, the different effects of the promotional tactics, the complexity and process of purchase decisions, the perception of risk for retail purchase, the different market segments based upon purchase behavior, how retail managers may improve their chance of business success.

From the research findings, it can be concluded that there are different types of consumers existing in India.

They are:

Economic Consumers

Hedonist Consumers

Moralistic Consumers

Active and Inactive Consumers

Definite and Indefinite Consumers

Individualistic Consumers

Recreational Consumers

The understanding and insights about the above defined types of consumers enables retailers to increase the footfalls and hence their business.

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Notes

¹Ahmadabad is the economic hub of Gujarat state in India.

²Q&A stands for question and answer

³India Retail Forum 2008 which was held on September 16-18, as its annual convention in Mumbai

⁴Kishore Biyani is a CEO, Future Group, one of the India's largest listed retailers.

⁵Hasan M., Issar A., Ojha G., & Singh B. P., 'The Indian retail bazaar', published their work in Brand strategy, November 2006, pp. 36-39

⁶Source: Brown & Reid 1997; Westbrook and Black 1985. Adapted from, 'Sinha, P.K. & Uniyal, D. P. 2007, Managing Retailing, New Delhi, Oxford University Press

⁷Rational Consumer, accessed on January 5, 2010, <http://www.oppapers.com/essays/Rational-Consumer/177411>

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⁹To develop the insight, referred, 'Why buy ethically' - Ethical Consumer. Retrieved 2007-05-03, from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ethical_consumerism, [assessed on January 5, 2010].